

Language Shift Dynamics: Challenges and Solutions

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- 1) factors that contribute to language shift
- 2) challenges that language shift presents
- 3) solutions and strategies to mitigate the negative effects of language shift.
- 4) The importance of preserving linguistic diversity

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Annotation. In today's era of globalization, it is natural for every nation, every independent country, to secure its national interests, and in this regard, first of all, to preserve and develop its culture, ancient values, and mother tongue.

Key words: Era of globalization, national interests, preservation of mother tongue, newspapers-magazines, official documents in offices-organizations.

In today's era of globalization, it is natural for every nation, every independent country, to secure its national interests, and in this regard, first of all, to preserve and develop its culture, ancient values, and mother tongue. But we still have a lot of work to do to preserve the purity of our language.

First of all, it is a pity that we have not completely switched to the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin script, and the Krill alphabet is still used in official documents in

newspapers and magazines. In addition, there are still cases of journalists speaking in dialect or slurring foreign words in various programs broadcast on television. Such problems are also found in movies and radio broadcasts.

Another problem: some of the intellectuals who have a higher education, even a candidate's or a doctorate, cannot write four lines of text in their mother tongue. You feel sorry for the "intellectuals" whose father is Uzbek, whose mother is Uzbek, who is Uzbek himself, but who is literate in Russian, who has at least learned English perfectly, but who does not know Uzbek, his mother tongue. Let him learn a foreign language, but he must also respect his own language. Sometimes the employees working in the management offices also say that it is difficult to write in their own language. If you look at some documents, it can be seen that it was first written in Russian, and then translated into the state language.

Keeping our language pure means not allowing inappropriate words to be inserted into it. However, some artists try to stick English or other language words next to Uzbek words, considering that it is their own way and sometimes conforming to world standards. Is it not possible to name the programs "KameRadar" and "Start up club" on "Yoshlar" TV in our language? After all, these shows are intended for Uzbek viewers, right? Also, isn't it possible to name programs such as "MTV showkids", "TV-Sale", "M-news", "Voydod, karaoke", "Kozgolonshow" with catchy words in our language on the "Milliy" TV channel? After all, our young people get information and spiritual wealth mainly through television, right?! Such artificial names spoil not only our language, but also our hearts. The task of English teachers is not only to teach learners or to focus more on their English language skills such as reading, writing, listening and speaking, but also to instill in them a

passion for English, it also consists of helping and encouraging by giving good attitude and great motivation. Despite this, teachers today face a number of difficulties and obstacles in teaching English. These are the following:

1. Disrupted classroom environment. The environment is very important in teaching and learning English. A disturbing atmosphere in the classroom distracts students and negatively affects language learning.

A suitable and comfortable environment is the basic need for teaching English. If the environment is not suitable and comfortable for the students, it will destroy the English language learning process. In teaching English, mainly teachers face such an unfavorable environment.

2. Limited teaching resources. Teaching anything, not just English, depends on many resources. Teachers often face such problems. That is, teachers are not provided with the necessary resources to learn English effectively. Without them, it will be very difficult to teach and learn the language.

Resources include speakers, microphones, projectors, computer systems, and other types of digital devices. With these, teaching and learning will be more effective and interesting.

3. The number of students in the class. Having a large number of students in the classroom creates a lot of anxiety and stress for teachers. Because in order to teach a large number of students, teachers need to make more effort and hard work.

Problems that arise on the part of many students are as follows:

1. They make noise and disturb the teacher.

2. It will be difficult to manage the students in the class.

3. It will be very difficult to attract a large number of students to study.

4. Educational resources will not be enough for all students.

4. Limited time. Time is very important in learning and teaching English. Teachers need time to observe their students and teach them at their level. However, there is very little class time allocated for teaching this subject. This is a very difficult task for teachers to teach in a short time.

5. The fact that students are attached to teachers. Another notable problem that teachers face is that students are completely dependent on teachers. They do not try to learn and speak themselves. Students always turn to teachers to help them learn and give them the right answers.

They do not try to correct words and sentences when speaking English.

In this problem, students have not learned the technical terms of using different tenses and words in English.

6. Students who are bored and not interested in learning English. Students' boredom and lack of interest in learning English is also a problem facing teachers.

Sometimes students are not interested in learning English and attending lectures.

Then they try to engage in other activities.

Sometimes they disturbed the teachers by talking to others and doing other meaningless things during the lecture.

Along with problems and difficulties, of course, there are no solutions to them. The following are the best solutions:

1. Educational competitions in classes

Competitions play a very important role in learning English. It forces students to learn English, such as debates, quizzes, etc.

Various competitions among students make learning English interesting and encourage them to participate in competitions and win among their colleagues.

Competitions make teaching English easier for teachers. Teachers should organize competition activities among students.

2. Use of multimedia during the lecture

Often English teachers use old and traditional methods in teaching.

But new devices and gadgets designed specifically for educational purposes can improve English teaching and learning. Teachers should use multimedia tools in their lectures.

3. Teaching through games

Games are the type of activity that engages students the most. Games also play a very important role in education and learning. There are many educational games that can be played in the classroom with students. Games help to increase vocabulary. There is a game of placing the missing word in different types of sentences. It builds vocabulary a lot. Students understand the types of words and their meaning and their place in the sentence. In the process of learning English, teachers should use it to play games in the classroom.

4. Manage lesson and timetable rules

Teachers should make class rules and schedules, and students should follow them. Rules and discipline play a very important role in learning English. Students should turn off their mobile phones, not talk to their friends, go to class. They should come on time and do their homework on time and submit it to the teacher. If students violate any of the rules, they should be fined or their parents should be contacted.

Educating the current young generations and making them highly competent is not only the teacher's duty, but also depends on the family environment and the attention of the neighborhood. Scientific studies and researches show that 70% of all the information that a person receives during his life before the age of 6 shows the importance of preschool education in the development of a child's personality. At the meeting held by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev on August 16, 2017, in order to determine the measures for 100% inclusion of 5-6-year-old children in preschool educational institutions, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan The decision "On organizing the activities of the Ministry of Education" was adopted. And in these institutions, it was decided to teach English from an early age. The reason is, as our ancestors used to say, "knowledge acquired in youth is a pattern carved in stone." This is not for nothing, as shown in this article, the earlier learning begins, it will lead to the elimination of some of the above-mentioned problems and difficulties, and the easier acquisition of language skills and competencies. it is. Especially if this knowledge, skills, skills are absorbed through various games and educational activities, the child develops foreign languages as naturally as his mother tongue. Educational games not only form knowledge, skills and abilities in a child, but at the same time, they ensure the child's

healthy physical development, mentally refresh, strengthen self-confidence, and have a great opportunity to form social relations with others. it gives mak. At the same time, the existing problems in language teaching, which are indicated in this article, that is, the problems between teachers and young generations, can be eliminated based on the mentioned solutions.

REFERENCES

1. S.T. Sa'diev Z.S. Ochilov XLIII International scientific and practical conference "International scientific review of the problem and perspective of modern science and education". "Po temu Faktory, vliyayushchie na kachestvo muzykalnogo obrazovaniya". March 25-26, 2018 (American Boston). <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/deed.en>
2. S.T. Sa'diev ACADEMICIA An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal "The basic law - rules of imaging" Vol. 11, Issue 5, May 2021 saarjournal@gmail.com
3. S. T. Sa'diev "Methods of Middle Ages Eastern Miniature Schools" International Scientific Journal "Science and Innovation" (ISSN: 2181-3337) Issue 2, 2022.